

Role of AI in Enhancing the Efficiency and Effectiveness of Shop and Delivery Propositions in Smart Cities

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Abstract

With increased urbanization, governments are considering increasing the development of smart cities to solve the issues associated with urbanization. Technology implementation in different aspects of the smart city ecosystems is given priority. This research explored the role of implementing some of the current technologies, AI, ML, and PA, in a specific aspect in smart cities, shops, and delivery propositions. Through the TAM framework, this research draws information from previously published papers. The collected information is thematically categorized into the significance and challenges of these technologies. The research found these technologies offer solutions in inventory management, logistics, and demand forecasting in supply chain management, provide customers with personalized shopping experiences, enhance customer support and engagement, and promote sustainability and social equity. However, implementing these technologies posed some changes - data security and privacy issues, regulatory issues, data quality and availability, and financial problems. The research provides recommendations to the policy-makers, city management, and businesses and proposes future research based on the identified research limitations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Predictive Analytics, Smart City, and Shop and Delivery Propositions

Introduction

Smart cities are at the forefront of integrating technology into their systems to improve most aspects of urban life. One of the aspects of focus by the smart cities is the enhancement of the shop and delivery propositions, and the smart cities are working towards integrating Machine Learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Predictive Analytics (PA) innovations in this aspect. For clarity, in this context, a smart city is an urban area that engages in data collection and analysis and uses the insight of these data to improve transportation, health, energy, education, security, business, and other aspects using innovative and sustainable technologies. ML is a computer science branch that uses data and algorithms to recognize patterns and make predictions. AI is a human intelligence simulation by machines to aid in artificial reasoning, learning, and problem-solving. ML is part of AI, but AI includes other methods that do not entirely depend on the data but on logic and rules. PA is a technique employing data, algorithms, and ML to predict future outcomes based on the existing data patterns. AI, ML, and PA are potential innovative

technologies that can help smart cities enhance shop and delivery propositions. This research paper explores the current landscape and application of AI, ML, and PA and their potential to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in smart city shops and delivery propositions.

Background

Data and technology are the most important tools in smart cities to uphold efficiency, effectiveness, convenience, and sustainability in urban services. In the smart city ecosystem, shops and delivery propositions are among the fundamental sectors. E-commerce, supply chain optimization, last-mile delivery, and customer experiences are common aspects of shop and delivery propositions. The increasing applications of ML, AI, and PA in various industries have increased efficiency and effectiveness in such fields. Nonetheless, in the field of shop and delivery in smart cities, these three technologies seem to hold the key to the revolutionization of this sector. These technologies promise to improve and optimize traditional inventory management, route planning, forecasting demand, and streamlining personalized shopping experiences.

Related Work

This section investigates previous research findings concerning ML, AI, and PA in shop and delivery propositions. The literature review places this paper in the context of continuing research on using these technologies in upholding efficiency and effectiveness in smart cities. Through investigations of previous research, this paper identifies the potential of ML, AI, and PA in enhancing shop and delivery propositions and the gaps existing in this field.

ML technology is essential in the current era for inventory management. Shops require efficient inventory management to avoid wasting money, resources, and space on obsolete inventory. Research by Verma et al. (2016) identifies that the integration of ML in inventory management improved performance, though it might present some challenges based on the nature of the research approach. As Kartal et al. (2016) proposed, machine learning algorithms integrate well with decision-making approaches to effectively conduct multi-attribute inventory analysis. Henceforth, machine learning techniques improve inventory management, and more research is vital to establish an effective integration of ML in inventory management.

In smart cities, there is always a high demand for fast, reliable, and flexible delivery services; hence, last-mile delivery is vital. Several factors affect last-mile delivery, like traffic congestion, environmental impacts, delivery costs, and customer satisfaction. Organizations use technological approaches, especially AI, ML, and PA, to optimize the planning, execution, and monitoring of last-mile deliveries. Research by Lau (2014) found that congestion was the major challenge in smart cities that distracted the efficiency of last-mile delivery. In the research, Lau suggested the application of AI in the planning framework to enhance real-time clustering and routing decision-making. With growing urbanization, smart cities are using AI Systems (AIS) to create an intelligent transport system that will allow the flow of goods and services to the end user (Agarwal, 2015). Conclusively, AI, ML, and PA are employed in smart cities to enhance intelligent transport, improving last-mile delivery.

Predictive analytics has the potential to provide customers with personalized shopping. PA uses data and AI to synchronize and anticipate customer preferences, needs, and behaviors – this allows the shops to offer customized products, experiences, and services to the customer. PA uses my data models through statistical approaches using machine learning algorithms and AI techniques to accomplish personalized shopping (Duhigg, 2013). Additionally, PA can forecast demand and hence guide price optimization. In their research, Ferreira et al. (2015) used machine learning techniques to optimize pricing decisions in an online fashion industry. They found that the creation of a data-based algorithm potentially optimized the pricing. Consequently, the implementation of PA in the shops will achieve the goal of providing customers with personalized shopping and helping the shops optimize their prices in alignment with demand.

Among the core goals of smart cities are sustainability and social equity considerations. Concerning the shops and delivery propositions, the sustainability goal can be achieved by employing environmentally sustainable strategies like transportation route optimization, emissions reduction, and waste minimization. AI, ML, and PA technologies reduce traffic congestion in the city and gas emissions by using real-time data on traffic and weather conditions (Barone et al., 2014). The ML technology minimizes waste generation and disposal by analyzing data patterns and behaviors to promote personalized and environmental incentives for reducing and recycling waste. Safety and health are critical in smart cities, and through PA, data on crime trends and health risks are analyzed to prevent potential threats and emergencies (Elmaghrabyss & Losavio, 2014). A shop and delivery proposition's efficiency and effectiveness are achievable if sustainability and social equity considerations are attained in smart cities.

Towards implementing technology in smart cities to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of shops and delivery propositions, smart cities face a couple of challenges. The most significant challenges include data security, infrastructure, and regulatory issues. Exploration of the smart city frame presents complexity and a clear insight that the success of a single sector in the smart city requires collaboration with multiple stakeholders. The success of implementing AI, ML, and PA in shops and delivery propositions depends on the cooperation among the shop owners, the city management, policy-makers, people and community, and the related sectors like the transport industry (Chourabi et al., 2012). In the case of big data management, small enterprise organizations, and even big organizations face challenges in data management.

Also, no robust framework exists for data and information sharing among organizations. Additionally, databases used in smart cities have sensitive citizens and government information that might present security and privacy issues when this data is shared among organizations (Al Nuaimi et al., 2015). As such, enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of shops and delivery propositions through technological implementation requires the resolution of the identified challenges.

Table 1:Summary of AI, ML, & PA Applications in Shop and Delivery Propositions

Type of Technology	Role in Shops and Delivery propositions	References
ML	Inventory management enhancement Optimizing stock levels Reducing stock and space wastage Route optimization Cost-effectiveness in delivery systems	(Verma et al., 2016; Kartal et al., 2016)
AI	Last-mile delivery effectiveness Customer Support and Engagement Personalized shopping experiences Increasing sales Increasing customer satisfaction	(Lau, 2014; Agarwal, 2015)
PA	Customers personalized shopping Forecasting demand Logistics optimization Enhancing last-mile delivery Accuracy enhancement supply chain management Promoting safety and security Optimizing sustainability and social equity	(Duhigg, 2013; Ferreira et al., 2015; Elmaghrabyss & Losavio, 2014; Barone et al., 2014)

Methodology

a) Theoretical Framework:

This research employs the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to analyze the user acceptance of AI, ML, and PA in shop and delivery propositions and the broader integration of these technologies in the urban context. Davis developed TAM in 1989 to use this framework to assess user acceptance and adoption of new technology. This framework works under two primary constructs: perceived usefulness and ease of use (Silva, 2015). The former expresses how the users of the suggested technology believe it will enhance job performance or make their job easier. Simultaneously, the latter reflects the degree to which the perceived technology users believe that implementation of the technology will be free from effort and complications. In this research, TAM explores the perception of the shop and delivery service users and providers on the utility and ease of use of AI, ML, and PA technologies.

Figure 1: Representation of TAM

b) Data Collection

This research collected data from previously published research papers. The inclusion criteria for these papers were to have been published within five years and to have relevant information to the current research. The selection of credible resources entailed a comprehensive literature review by searching these resources from academic databases like Google Scholar, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, ResearchGate, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science. The criterion of searching for relevant resources from these databases entailed using keywords including Artificial intelligence, Machine Learning, Predictive Analytics, Smart City, and Shop and Delivery Propositions. The identified papers were screened for quality and their fitness to this study by checking into factors such as whether they were peer-reviewed, published in recognized journals, credibility and validity of their content, and their relevance to their current research. The papers that met the inclusion criterion were selected.

c) Data Analysis

In adherence with the research theoretical framework, the identified literature was categorized as TAM-based Studies. These studies looked into the perceived usefulness and ease of use of AI, ML, and PA in shop and delivery propositions; this was essential to assess the user acceptance of the technology in the context of shop and delivery services. Overall, the results obtained were streamlined towards exploring the current landscape and application of AI, ML, and PA and their potential to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in smart city shops and delivery propositions.

Data collected from the TAM-based category was thematically categorized to identify the perceived usefulness and ease of use of the three technologies within smart cities. Patterns of positive and negative relationships between user acceptance and the perceived ease of use of the proposed technologies were identified. The users and providers of shop and delivery services

perceived that implementation of the AI, ML, and PA in shops and delivery proposition had the following significance:

- Improved inventory management
- Reduced costs and wastage associated with stockouts or overstocking.
- Optimized logistics.
- Optimized route, hence enhancing last-mile delivery.
- Faster and cheaper deliveries.
- More accurate demand forecasting in supply chain management.
- Increased sales and profits in the shops.
- Enhanced customer support and engagement.
- Enhanced personalized shopping experiences.
- Upheld sustainability and social equity.

However, the users and providers of the shops and delivery services perceived that the implementation of AI, ML, and PA in shops and delivery propositions in the smart city ecosystem had the following challenges:

- Data privacy and security
- Regulatory issues
- Data quality and availability
- Financial problems in implementing and maintaining the technology

The collected data identified that the users and providers of the shop and delivery services in the smart city ecosystem had more positive perceptions of the implementation of AI, ML, and PA in the shops and delivery propositions.

Figure 2: Acceptance and Ease of Use Perception on the Proposed Technology

Discussion

The research found that implementing AI, ML, and PA is already continuing in smart cities, and shops and delivery propositions are among the sectors consuming these technologies. In its early applications, ML significantly improved inventory management (Verma et al., 2016; Kartal et al., 2016). ML optimizes stock levels, reduces stock wastage, and efficiently uses minimal storage space. Henceforth, the shops benefit from improved inventory management and save costs and wastes associated with stockouts or overstocking.

AI, ML, and PA significantly optimize logistics by enhancing supply chain management and last-mile delivery (Agarwal, 2015; Duhigg, 2013). With close reference to AI, research shows that AI plays a significant role in enhancing last-mile delivery. Smart cities present with traffic congestion challenges, so shipping goods or services to customers becomes challenging. This challenge of traffic congestion also leads to the escalation of delivery costs in smart cities. However, data show that with AI-driven solutions, the efficiency of last-mile delivery improves by applying real-time clustering and routing challenges approaches (Lau, 2014). With AI-driven resolutions, delivery services in smart cities are becoming faster and cheaper.

Using the three technologies has enhanced customer support and engagement. Research shows that PA significantly enhances personalized shopping experiences in smart city shops. Through analyzing customer data, AI and ML systems learn the customers purchasing behaviors, and through predictive analytics, the chances of suggesting the products and services preferred by the customer are high (Agarwal, 2015; Duhigg, 2013). Conclusively, enhancing customer support and engagement and providing personalized shopping experience contributes to customer satisfaction, hence upholding customer loyalty.

Research shows that PA is an efficient technology in demand forecasting. Shops and delivery providers face challenges in forecasting the time of the day, week, month, or season when a specific commodity or service might be in higher or lower demand beyond the optimal threshold. However, through learning the customer purchasing behavior, PA forecasts demand provides a more accurate demand forecasting in supply chain management, and guides shops in price optimization based on the demand for their products and services (Ferreira et al., 2015). Henceforth, through PA, shops and delivery proportions increase sales and profits.

The research data show that implementing these three technologies aligns with smart cities' sustainability and social equity goals (Monfaredzadeh & Krueger, 2015). These technologies are vital in reducing traffic congestion, carbon emissions, waste generation, and promoting environmental incentives (Barone et al., 2014). Additionally, smart cities require security to ensure businesses run smoothly, shops and delivery services included (Hancke et al., 2012). These technologies have proven to enhance the efficiency of data analysis on crime trends, contributing to the early detection of possible criminal activities and enhancing safety and security in smart cities.

Despite the advantages of implementing AI, ML, and PA in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities, implementing these technologies presents challenges worth noting. Some common challenges identified were data privacy and security, regulatory issues, data quality and

availability, and financial problems. The challenge of data privacy and security is significant in that data collected from individuals by organizations can easily be exposed to misuse by a third party, sold to a third party, or shared with the third party without seeking the user's consent. If such an incident occurs, there will be a violation of human privacy and confidentiality (Martinez-Balleste et al., 2013). Additionally, data regulatory bodies may impose policies that will be difficult to meet by several organizations within the smart cities; hence, data collection for the effective operation of the technologies may not be necessary. Data quality and availability might be challenging because the smart city stores the data in databases. There is no guarantee that organizations will be allowed by the smart city governance to access these databases. Still, this data might not effectively perform functions intended by the shops and delivery providers. Lastly, implementing these technologies requires a high startup and maintenance capital, which might not be available and convenient for small and middle enterprises (Monzon, 2015).

Recommendations

Considering the information from the research findings and discussions, the following recommendations are essential to the policy-makers and businesses in smart cities.

- Smart city governance should promote collaboration among the city stakeholders, government bodies, technology providers, businesses, and planners to address the challenges faced during AI, ML, and PA technologies implementation.
- Smart cities should establish robust data governance policies and regulations to solve the problem of data privacy and security concerns. These policies and regulations should cover data security and privacy during data sharing in the smart city initiatives.
- Smart cities should invest in training and enhancing skill development to equip city businesses and personnel with essential skills in leveraging AI, ML, and PA technologies in shops and delivery propositions.
- Smart cities should contact pilot projects within certain shops and delivery propositions to demonstrate the benefits of implementing these technologies to businesses. These pilot projects will monitor and adjust the technologies' implementation, encouraging wider adoption.
- Smart cities should raise public awareness of the significance of AI-driven decision-making in shops and delivery propositions; this will bring on board the consumers and businesses to test the personalized shopping experiences and uphold sustainable delivery options, enhancing consumer and provider acceptance.

Conclusion

AI, ML, and PA technologies can potentially revolutionize the shop and delivery proposition in smart cities. These technologies are currently offering solutions in improving inventory management, optimizing logistics, route, and last-mile delivery, providing customers with personalized shopping experiences and providing enhanced customer support and engagement, enhancing customer satisfaction, promoting sustainability and social equity, and facilitating more accurate demand forecasting in supply chain management hence increasing sales and profits in the shops. However, these advantages can be effectively and efficiently achieved if the challenges facing the implementation of these technologies are solved – data security and

privacy issues, regulatory issues, data quality and availability, and financial problems. Effective integration of AI, ML, and PA in smart city ecosystems requires the readiness of the smart cities. Therefore, smart cities need to strengthen their technology infrastructure, data governance, citizen engagement, and sustainability to soften the implementation of these technologies.

This research had some limitations, hence the need for further research. The research relied on existing literature and data from previously published papers. This approach limits the findings' depth and specificity. Hence, future research may benefit from empirical data and smart city stakeholders' perspectives. Another limitation is that of ethical and social implications. This research briefly explored ethical and social considerations when implementing AI, ML, and PA in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities. Future research could benefit from exploring more details on these issues by diving into specific issues like algorithm bias, privacy concerns, and how technology impacts employment.

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